

SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF SYRDARYA REGION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE COMPETITIVENESS OF YOUTH IN THE LABOR MARKET

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Abstract

This thesis analyzes the socio-economic development processes of Syrdarya region, their impact on the labor market, in particular, on the competitiveness of young people. The article highlights the economic reforms, investment projects, employment policy, and the importance of the system of vocational training and retraining of young people in the region.

Keywords:

unemployment, youth competitiveness, labor market, Syrdarya region, employment, efficiency, regulatory system.

Introduction

Today, economic growth, social stability, and job creation are among the top priorities in all regions of Uzbekistan, including Syrdarya region. The region's economic potential, transport infrastructure, industrial and agricultural opportunities play an important role in creating new jobs for young people and shaping them as competitive personnel in the labor market.

Discussion

The social development of the region affects the competitiveness of youth. According to statistics, in 2025, the number of labor resources was 167,2 thousand people, of which 369.5 thousand people (75.8%) were economically active. According to the analysis, the number of employed people decreased by 6,5% during 2018-2025. To gain a general understanding of the situation in the region in terms of increasing the competitiveness of unemployed youth, it is proposed to consider the dynamics of indicators for 2017-2025 presented below (Figure 1).

Figure 1 shows that the number of young people in the region decreased by 15 percent during 2017-2025. Young people make up 26.1 percent of the permanent population in the region. An analysis of this indicator by year shows that it has not been uniform. For example, in 2017, the share of young people in the population was 28.8 percent, while in 2023 this indicator was 26.1 percent, or a decrease of 2.7 points.

In accordance with the proposed methodology for assessing the competitiveness of unemployed youth, the dynamics of the number of young labor resources in 2017-2025 is the first indicator in the study (Table 1).

Table 2.3 shows that during 2017-2023, the number of labor resources in the region increased by 11.7 percent, and the number of young people in the labor force increased by 5.5 percent.

In Syrdarya region, 78.4 percent of the labor force is economically active, and the remaining 21.6 percent is economically inactive. The number of young people in the economically active population of the region increased by 10.0 percent, but the growth rate of their number in the employed population was somewhat lower.

Table 1. Changes in the number of young people in labor resources and their composition in Syrdarya region, thousand people*

Indicators	Years							In 2023 compared to 2017, %
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	
Labor force	475,2	480,5	484,5	485,0	489,5	487,4	492,2	103.5
Including: youth	276	277	278	279	280	284	290	105
Economically active population	371.9	390.7	385.9	378.2	372.1	369.5	364.8	98
Including: youth	212	215	218	219	220	222	230	108.4
Employed population	353,1	354,2	350,1	45,2	334,1	335,0	338,0	95.7
Including: youth	207	207	208	208	208	209	246	118.8
Unemployed	18,8	36,5	35,8	36,6	38,0	34,5	26,8	142.5
Including: youth	10,9	10,8	10,8	10,8	10,8	10,8	21,2	194.4

Over the past five years, based on the existing socio-economic conditions, employers (enterprises and organizations) have been forming complex requirements for employees. In particular, the demand for qualified personnel is increasing in the construction, trade, small business, finance and banking, and energy sectors. These requirements are determined not by the age of employees, but by their professional skills and level of qualification. Enterprises are currently in need of young specialists who have mastered modern technologies, are highly qualified, and correspond to existing vacancies.

Despite this, between 2011 and 2018, educational institutions have been training specialists who do not fully meet the requirements of the labor market and have low practical training. This situation is mainly due to the fact that insufficient attention is paid to the practical aspects of education, and internships are often conducted only as a formality. As a result, many graduates of higher

education institutions in the region are forced to work in areas that do not correspond to their specialization. Over the past decade, the direction and quality of the education system for training specialists have not been closely linked to economic requirements and have not sufficiently reflected their needs. This, in turn, is explained by the lack of cooperation between higher education institutions and employers. Such a disconnection leads to the formation of misconceptions about young personnel in the labor market, as a result of which the employment rate of young specialists decreases and the number of young people engaged in unproductive work increases.

Studying the effectiveness and developing proposals:

Having analyzed the youth labor market in Syrdarya region, we have identified a number of ways to combat unemployment:

1. Creating a rating of industries and professions with high demand for labor, which will have a positive effect on the level of graduates in all specialties. This will reduce the number of unemployed graduates due to reduced competition among graduates. It is also possible to limit the number of graduates in specialties with a surplus of labor.

2. Develop a special “National Methodology for Assessing Youth Competitiveness”;

3. Introduce a self-assessment system on digital platforms;

4. Create a map of youth skills across regions;

5. Adjust grant, loan and employment processes based on the assessment results.

Conclusion

As a result of monitoring youth employment in Syrdarya region, it can be concluded that there are a number of negative trends in the region in terms of changes in the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of young labor resources, leading to a decrease in their competitiveness.

In summary, skills mismatch, rapid population growth, limited private sector growth, and lack of resources in remote areas of the country are the main causes of youth unemployment. However, by reforming education, attracting foreign investment, and focusing on high-demand sectors such as IT, this problem can be solved and more jobs can be created for young people.

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